

ASSESSMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION METHODS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: This article describes the methods of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities, the theoretical issues of determining and evaluating the effectiveness of marketing are unique, and the approaches to it are different. Definitions of the economic efficiency of marketing activities using both qualitative and quantitative indicators in the determination and evaluation of marketing efficiency, several methods of determining the economic efficiency of promotional activities are proposed, and the types of marketing control in increasing efficiency are practically based. they were given brief scientific information. The article also reflects the relationship between the main goals of marketing and the main goals of the company.

Keywords: Marketing, marketing goal, marketing tasks, marketing types, quality method, Innovative marketing, quantitative method, sociological method, Regressive and correlation method.

Introduction: In the conditions of today's rapidly developing market economy, with the rapid changes in the external environment and the complexity of the market activities of enterprises, it is important to constantly monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of marketing services, including business processes, meeting the needs of consumers, improving the quality of service on every front earns.

Evaluating the effectiveness of marketing in the activities of enterprises is a difficult task, the impact of the service provided to consumers by the service of the marketing department cannot always be measured, and the value created does not give clear results.

Despite the fact that marketing specialists have paid enough attention to the problems of enterprise efficiency, marketing service efficiency, there is still no clearly structured model, methods and system of indicators that allow evaluating marketing activity.

Marketing (English: market — "market", "movement in the market", "activity") — a form of organization and management of production and sale of goods by the enterprise. The term "marketing" was introduced into use in the 60s of the 19th century by Mc Govern.

One of the scientists in the field of marketing Philip Kotler defines marketing as "the science and art of studying, creating, and delivering value to profitably satisfy existing market needs."

"Marketing is managing and meeting the demand for goods, services, organizations, territories and ideas in advance"

"Marketing is identifying, predicting and creating the needs and wants of consumers. It is the process of organizing all of a company's resources to satisfy the company and the consumer with the greatest benefit." Marketing is the process of creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging value propositions for customers, clients, partners, and society. Marketing identifies unmet needs and wants. It defines and measures the identified market size and profit opportunities. Simply put, marketing is the identification of gaps, problems, and shortages in

the market and providing the right solution. Every organization and company should use marketing. Marketing is the main cornerstone for the development of businesses. Purpose of Marketing: From the points made above, it is clear that marketing is not a set of measures aimed at selling products, but it is a much broader concept that covers all aspects of business management.

They believe that the goal of marketing is the maximum growth of production and the main factor in the enrichment of the enterprise is the promotion of high consumption. In other words, the more people buy and the more they consume, the happier they are. However, some people doubt the idea that an increase in material wealth is a sign of achieving great happiness. Therefore, the goal of marketing is not only to achieve the maximum possible consumption.

Analysis and results: There are several approaches to the formation of criteria and indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities. Some experts believe that the concept of marketing management is the basis of the criteria for evaluating the effectiveness.

Types of marketing. The specific forms and content of marketing come from the characteristics of the enterprise, its internal capabilities and external conditions. Here, marketing and all other intermediate types of activities merge into a single directed process to achieve set goals, which in turn determines the movement of various types of marketing.

Table 1

Classification of marketing types.

<i>Classification symbol</i>	<i>Marketing type</i>	<i>Marketing content</i>
1. Validity period	1.1. Strategic marketing	A complex of works on the formation of the firm's strategy based on the strategic segmentation of the market, the improvement of the quality of goods, the development of production and the forecasting of the strategy of competitiveness standards.
	1.2. Tactical marketing	Complex of activities on tactical (short-term) segmentation of the market, promotion of advertising and sales of goods.
2. Field of application	2.1. Marketing ideas with a public nature	Developing, implementing and monitoring the implementation of programs to achieve acceptance of a social idea, action or practice by a target group (or target groups).
	2.2. Places Marketing	Activities to create, maintain or change the customer's attitude towards the location of particular places, objects.
	2.3. Internal marketing	Marketing done within the firm to train and motivate customer-facing staff.
	2.4. Organizational marketing	Activities aimed at creating, maintaining or changing the attitude and behavior of all individuals and organizations of interest to this firm.
	2.5. International (global) marketing	International activity of the firm.

3. The area of Khatti-hara floors	3.1. Consumer marketing	Marketing between firms and final consumers, individuals or families.
	3.2. Industrialized marketing	Marketing between two firms (legal entities).
	3.3. Social marketing	Marketing to meet the social needs of people by budget (state) organizations that do not set profit as their goal.

Based on the theory of effectiveness of marketing activity, it is analyzed in several ways in the process of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing service.

As a rule, the concepts of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities and the effectiveness of marketing services can be defined as follows: what is the purpose of the evaluation? Who are the results for? where and how to use the results? and others. These concepts mentioned above are closely related concepts and complement each other. As a result of our research and studies, the following methods of determining the effectiveness of marketing activities are recommended by scientists and researchers to date:

Digital marketing - (also known as Internet marketing) is a component of marketing that uses the Internet and computers, mobile phones, and other digital technologies that connect to the Internet to promote products and services. Its development in the 1990s and 2000s changed the way brands and businesses used technology for marketing. As digital platforms become more and more integrated into marketing plans and everyday life and as people increasingly use digital devices instead of visiting physical stores, search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), content Marketing, influencer marketing, content automation, campaign marketing, data-driven marketing, e-commerce marketing, social media marketing (SMM), direct email marketing, display advertising, e-books and optical discs, and games have become commonplace. Digital marketing also includes non-Internet channels that provide digital media such as television, mobile phones (SMS and MMS), callbacks, and mobile ringtones on hold. Covering channels beyond the Internet also differentiates digital marketing from the science of online advertising. That is, digital marketing differs from "online advertising" in that it includes some listed non-internet platforms in addition to the internet.

Fig. 1. Methods of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities.

The quality method includes the use of marketing control and audit, during which it is a comprehensive analysis of all threats and opportunities through the results of SWOT analysis of the external environment of the organization, as well as the internal environment. Results-oriented marketing control and audit, analysis of the qualitative aspects of the organization's activities are covered.

A quantitative method of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities is marketing and advertising from the gross profit received after marketing expenses requires comparison of costs with removals, which represent the final financial results of the organization's activities.

The sociological method of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities is aimed at using the tools of applied sociology - developing a sociological research program and conducting the research accordingly.

The point method of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activity allows to determine the effectiveness of an event by assigning a certain score for each criterion, taking into account compliance with the list of criteria, compliance of structures and processes with the marketing concept.

Method of statistical theory, is used to stochastically describe the reaction of consumers to changes in market conditions.

Table 2

The main objectives of marketing are interrelated with the main objectives of the firm.

Objectives	Indicators
Capture the market	Marketing, circulation, importance of product oil, new markets coverage
Profitability	Profit, return on equity, return on equity, return on total capital
Financial stability	Creditworthiness, liquidity, level of self-financing, capital structure
Social goals	Job satisfaction, level of income, social protection, social integration, personal development
Market position and prestige	Independence, image, relation to political conditions, recognition of society

The main goal of marketing is determined by the objective reasons and necessity of its emergence, formation and development. As mentioned above, marketing was first of all invented and created as a tool to get out of this crisis in the conditions of accumulation of goods, unsold and economic crisis. Its purpose is to solve extremely broad and complex issues. It is to adapt the production to the needs of the customer, achieving the balance of demand and supply, and bringing high profits to the enterprises and organizations that created it. To achieve this, it is necessary to solve important marketing tasks:

- study and determine the needs of buyers (consumers);

- study of internal and external requirements for goods;
- adaptation of the company's activities to the needs of customers;
- market research based on the information obtained about supply and demand;
- organization of advertising of goods, increasing the interest of buyers in buying goods;
- collection and analysis of data to carry out research of the company that creates or sells the product;

Summary: In a broad sense, many marketers view marketing as a business philosophy, that is, studying the market, price system, predicting and anticipating customer desires, and communicating effectively with them to satisfy consumer needs accordingly. they see as profit opportunities for their companies.

In conclusion, we can say that marketing is a very interesting field for entrepreneurs.

If you know how to evaluate the effectiveness of marketing activities, you can make good profit and be competitive in the market for a long time. The prospect for further research is the formulation of methodological approaches to determining the required level of the indicator of the effectiveness of the marketing strategy of the enterprise, the value of which would be able to predict the main performance indicators of the enterprise.

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